

A new level of confidence: biogeography, morphometry and ecology of enigmatic *Cyclopyxis puteus* Thomas, 1960 (Amoebozoa: Arcellinida: Netzeiliidae)

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Abstract: Testate amoebae *Cyclopyxis puteus* Thomas (1960) has a characteristic morphology, that makes the possibility of overlook or misidentification unlikely. Although this species has been found worldwide, its morphology, biometrics and ecological preferences are poorly understood. In this study, isolated material from Bulgaria was investigated by using light and scanning electron microscopy. Based on morphological and biometrical data, we provide an improved diagnosis of this enigmatic species. A summary of the geographical distribution and ecological preferences is provided.

Keywords: Bulgaria, distribution, protists, taxonomy, testate amoebae

Introduction

Genus *Cyclopyxis* Deflandre, 1929 comprises lobose testate amoebae with shells of agglutinated mineral particles, hemispherical in lateral and circular in ventral view. According to latest taxonomic reviews, it belongs to class Elardia, Order Arcellinida, Suborder Glutinoconcha, Infraorder Sphaerothecina and Family Netzeiliidae (Kang et al., 2019; Kosakyan et al., 2016;). Nowadays, genus *Cyclopyxis* contains approximately 80 species and subspecies (Nicholls, 2005) that can be found in various habitats like soils, leaf litter or mosses. Some of them are widely distributed with high population density in the environment (*Cyclopyxis eurystoma* Deflandre, 1929 and *Cyclopyxis kahli* Deflandre, 1929), while some rare species with restricted or patchy distribution have been described.

One of those rare and enigmatic species is *Cyclopyxis puteus* Thomas, 1960. According to the original description “ce cyclopyxis a l’aspect général et la couleur de *C. kahli* Defl., mais avec une taille bien plus considérable. Une autre particularité réside par la constitution spéciale du pseudostome, qui permettra de toujours le reconnaître facilement.

L’ouverture de ce pseudostome est placée à l’extrémité terminale d’un tube conique fortement invaginé à l’intérieur de la thèque. Ce pseudostome, vaguement circulaire, a un contour légèrement crénelé par la bordure granuleuse. En vue ventrale, le tube du pseudostome, étant large à sa base, dessine un double contour très apparent, car ce tube, observé à l’apic, va en se rétrécissant à l’intérieur de la thèque au niveau du pseudostome. Le revêtement ne présente rien de particulier; il est pierreux à grosses particules sur le dôme. Dimensions: diamètre 145-163 µm; hauteur 110-120 µm; pseudostome 25-35 µm; base du tube 45-50 µm; longueur du tube 28-30 µm.” (this species has the general appearance and colour of *C. kahli*, but with much larger size. Another feature is the special construction of a pseudostome, which allows to recognise it easily. The opening is situated at the terminal end of a strongly invaginated inside the shell conical tube. This roughly circular pseudostome has slightly serrated contours due to the grained edge. In ventral view, the tube of the pseudostome, being wide at the base, forms a very distinct double contour, because it narrows inward into the shell at the level of the pseudostome. The coating does not present anything particular; pieces of quartz, larger on the

dorsal side. Measurements: diameter 145–163 μm ; height 110–120 μm ; pseudostome 25–35 μm ; base of the tube 45–50 μm ; length of the tube 28–30 μm).

The characteristic morphology and large size of this species makes the possibility of overlook or misidentification unlikely. However, the registered data emphasises the difficulty of defining the distribution patterns. So far, *C. puteus* is reported worldwide but with infrequent findings and low number of specimens. The scarcity of records, on the other hand, leads to a poorly studied morphology, biometry and ecological preferences.

During the investigation of testate amoebae communities from soil mosses and beech's litter from Bulgaria, we found population of *C. puteus* with a high abundance. We carried out detailed light and scanning electron microscopy analyses with additional morphometric examination of the shells. Our primary aims were: 1) to examine the Bulgarian populations of *C. puteus* morphologically and biometrically; 2) to clarify its geographic distribution and ecological preferences.

Materials and methods

The samples were taken on 8.11.2022 from soil mosses, litter (Ao) and soil humus (Ah – 0–5 cm) of beech forests (*Fagus sylvatica* L.) near Plachkovtsi Village (N 42.79821 E 25.49891, 591 a.s.l.) (Fig. 1). The brown mountain-forest soil is the main soil type within the area. The collected material was washed and examined in petri dish. Isolation was made under stereomicroscope at 100x magnification.

Morphological characters and morphometric variables of 350 shells were studied with optical microscope “Amplival” (Zeiss-Jena) using 40x objective and 10x oculars lens. The light micrographs were taken using an Axio Imager M2-Carl Zeiss compound microscope with a digital camera (ProgRes C7) and specialised software (CapturePro Software 2.8). Helicon Focus 8 software was used for the stacked images. The following morphometric measurements were taken: diameter, depth (= height in the original description), external opening (= base of the tube), internal opening (= pseudostome) and invagination (= length of the tube). For each morphometric variable, we calculated following basic summary statistics: arithmetic mean, median (M), standard deviation (SD), standard error of mean (SE),

coefficient of variation in % (CV), extreme values (Min and Max). Statistical analysis was conducted using the computer program STATISTICA Software, Version 10.0 (StatSoft 2010).

For the comparative analysis of the morphometric data, we used microscopic slides fixed with Canada balsam from two spatially distant locations in Bulgaria: Borisova Gradina area (litter and humus of oak forest (*Quercus* spp.)) and the area close to Mechata Dupka Cave on the path to Treskavets Hut (litter and humus of beech forest (*Fagus sylvatica*)) (unpublished data) (Fig. 1). Additional measurements were taken of single specimens from Eastern Rhodopes (Bulgaria; unpublished data) and North Korea (unpublished data).

Scanning electron microscopy analysis was conducted, as part of the specimens were extracted by using a glass micropipette, washed several times in distilled water, mounted on coverslip and air-dried. The shells were coated evenly with gold in a vacuum coating unit. The micrographs were obtained by using a JEOL JSM-5510, operating at 10 kV.

Results and discussion

Biometry

The morphometric characterisations of *C. puteus* according to our studies are given in Table 1. Dimensions of the shell are: diameter 145–190 μm ; depth 93–145 μm ; external opening 42–65 μm ; internal opening 28–44 μm and invagination 39–57 μm . All measured shell parameters are moderately variable (CV between 5.21 and 10.0%). The most stable characters in this population are shell's diameter and depth (5.21 and 7.41, respectively), while internal opening and invagination have maximal values (9.53 and 10, respectively). External opening has an intermediate value of 8.20.

Analysis of the size frequency distribution shows that *C. puteus* is a size-monomorphic species with a relatively well-expressed main-size class of the basic shell characters (Fig. 2). For example, about three-quarters of all measured individuals (73%) have a diameter of shell within the limits of 160–180 μm , whereas only 17% have a diameter less than 160 μm and 10% – more than 180 μm (Fig. 2A). Regarding the shell's depth and diameter of external opening, most of the measured individuals also varied within

Fig. 1. Localities of *Cyclopyxis puteus* in Bulgaria. The examined population is indicated in red. Populations used as comparative material are marked as follows: green – Borisova Gradina area; blue – Mechata Dupka area.

close limits: depth of shell 105–135 μm (91%) and diameter of external opening 46–64 μm (96%) (Fig. 2 B, C). The presence of a well-expressed main-size class of the basic shell characters and the lack of the subsidiary peaks (bell-shaped curves) indicate a normal distribution. The average values of these characters are respectively 169.4 ± 0.47 (diameter), 119.8 ± 0.47 (depth) and 55.4 ± 0.24 (external opening). They fully correlate with the main-size classes of characters and testify to the monomorphism of the species.

Our results were compared with the morphometric dimensions of the other two populations from Bulgaria (Table 1). Mean values indicate overall larger size dimensions of the Plachkovtsi population. When comparing variability of all characters, analysed populations have moderate coefficient of variation: diameter (between 4.63 and 7.29); depth (6.96–9.08); external opening (7.87–11.75); internal opening (9.41–10.03) and

invagination (8.46–10 respectively for Borisova Gradina and Plachkovtsi; no invagination was measured for Mechata Dupka). The population with the lowest coefficient of variation was that of Borisova Gradina (with an exception of external opening), while Plachkovtsi's population has intermediate position.

Comparative analysis of the size frequency distribution confirms size-monomorphism of *C. puteus*, characterised by a main size class and a small size range. In the Fig. 3 is shown frequency analysis of shell diameter, which confirms larger dimensions of Plachkovtsi population, while “apparent” polymorphism of Mechata Dupka population is due to small number of measurements.

The above mentioned conclusions of comparative analysis are supported by the scatter plot of shell diameter versus shells depth (Fig. 4). All three populations have a linear relationship. Plachkovtsi and Mechata Dupka are characterised with moderate

Table 1. Morphometric characterisations of *C. puteus* from Plachkovtsi, Borisova Gradina and Mechata Dupka.

Characters	Popullation	Mean	M	SD	SE	CV	Min	Max	n
diameter	Plachkovtsi	169.44	170	8.82	0.47	5.21	145	190	350
	Borisova Gradina	156.26	155.7	7.23	0.67	4.63	133	180	117
	Mechata Dupka	153.69	155.7	11.2	1.47	7.29	134	179	58
depth	Plachkovtsi	119.84	120	8.88	0.47	7.41	93	145	350
	Borisova Gradina	103.8	102	7.22	2.28	6.96	96	121	10
	Mechata Dupka	105.13	107.5	9.54	2.88	9.08	94	120	11
external opening	Plachkovtsi	55.48	56	4.55	0.24	8.2	42	65	350
	Borisova Gradina	50.35	50	5.92	0.55	11.75	32	61	114
	Mechata Dupka	48.39	48	3.8	0.56	7.87	42	56	47
internal opening	Plachkovtsi	35.46	36	3.38	0.19	9.53	28	44	329
	Borisova Gradina	33.97	34	3.20	0.37	9.41	27	42	75
	Mechata Dupka	31.04	31	3.11	0.45	10.03	26	39	47
invagination	Plachkovtsi	47.35	47	4.73	0.52	10	39	57	84
	Borisova Gradina	32.44	34	2.74	0.91	8.46	28	36	9
	Mechata Dupka	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
depth/ diameter ratio	Plachkovtsi	0.71	0.7	0.048	0.003	6.79	0.55	0.86	350
	Borisova Gradina	0.67	0.66	0.05	0.016	7.44	0.63	0.79	10
	Mechata Dupka	0.7	0.7	0.032	0.01	4.56	0.65	0.77	11
external opening/ diameter ratio	Plachkovtsi	0.33	0.33	0.025	0.001	7.66	0.25	0.40	350
	Borisova Gradina	0.32	0.32	0.035	0.003	10.72	0.24	0.39	114
	Mechata Dupka	0.31	0.32	0.031	0.005	9.88	0.25	0.38	47
invagination/ depth ratio	Plachkovtsi	0.38	0.38	0.037	0.004	9.58	0.28	0.50	84
	Borisova Gradina	0.32	0.31	0.033	0.011	10.42	0.28	0.36	9
	Mechata Dupka	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

strength, while Borisova Gradina has almost horizontal slope that indicate a weak strength.

The summarised data of previous biometric records is given in Table 2. The results of the three examined populations correspond well with those given by other authors (Thomas 1960, Golemansky 1962, Bobrov & Mazei 2004, Vincke et al 2006, Todorov & Bankov 2019) and fall within biometrical framework of previous studies. Must be noted that in Bobrov & Mazei 2004 the values of diameter and depth are probably erroneously shifted.

The examination of solitary specimens from the Eastern Rhodopes and North Korea confirmed the above mentioned measurements with an exception of four shells (2 from each locality) with diameter over

200 µm. The measurements are as follows: Eastern Rhodopes: 1) diameter 203 µm; external opening 58 µm; internal opening 34 µm; 2) diameter 214 µm and North Korea: 1) diameter 210 µm; external opening 63 µm; internal opening 42 µm; 2) diameter 229 µm; external opening 75 µm.

Redescription

The original description of *C. puteus* (Thomas, 1960) is based on light microscopy with notes on the general appearance and structure of the pseudostome (Fig. 5). The number of measured individuals is not mentioned. The most comprehensive study to

Fig. 2. Histograms showing the size frequency distribution of the shell's diameter (A), depth (B) and external opening (C) in *Cyclopyxis puteus*.

improve this taxonomic characterisation was conducted by scanning electron microscopy and gives first data of species ultrastructure (Todorov & Bankov, 2019). Nevertheless, the number of examined specimens weren't enough to scope the phenotypic plasticity range. In addition, the analysed

data was from microscopic slides, where no information about degree of invagination was collected. The results of this study support and refine previous description. To clarify the description and avoid ambiguous terminology, we refer base of the tube (Thomas, 1960) and diameter of aperture (Todorov & Bankov, 2019) as external opening.

Shell circular in ventral and dorsal views, hemispherical in lateral, yellowish or brownish, composed mainly of quartz particles (larger on the dorsal side) (Fig. 6), embedded in a layer of organic cement with numerous small pores on the ventral and lateral surface (Fig. 7). The outline has a smooth surface. Internal opening circular, central and situated at the terminal end of a strongly invaginated inside the shell conical tube. External opening with larger diameter. Different diameters of external and internal openings, form a very distinct double contour with slightly serrated borders due to the grained edge.

Measurements: diameter 133–190 µm (occasionally up to 229 µm); depth 93–145 µm; external opening 32–65 µm (occasionally up to 75 µm); internal opening 26–46 µm; invagination 28–57 µm; depth/diameter ratio – 0.55–0.86; external opening/diameter ratio – 0.24–0.4; invagination/depth ratio – 0.28–0.5.

Geographic distribution

First discovered near Pessac in southwestern France by Thomas (1960), *C. puteus* has been recorded from many localities in Europe, including Belgium (Chardez, 1961; Chardez et al., 1987), Bulgaria (Deltshev et al., 1999; Todorov, 2001; Bankov, 2022; Todorov, unpublished), Czech Republic (Balik, 1994), France (Bonnet, 1972, 1993, Decloitre, 1977), Poland (Golemansky, 1970), Russia (Balik, 1992; Bobrov, 2001; Bobrov & Mazei, 2004; Payne et al., 2020; as fossil record in Bobrov et al., 2003, 2004), Slovakia (Balik, 1997) and in the area between Belgium, North France, Luxemburg and Netherland (no information for a particular country or sample point in Chardez & Lambert, 1981). It has also been reported in South America: Brazil and Paraguay (Bonnet, 1979); French Guiana (Coûteaux & Chardez, 1981) and Peru (Bobrov et al., 2019), Central America: Mexico (Bonnet, 1977a; Bobrov et al., 2013) as well as North America: Canada (Puytorac et al., 1972; Bonnet, 1974; Lousier, 1982; Beyens et al., 1990). Ad-

Fig. 3. Histograms showing the diameter frequency distribution of *Cyclopyxis puteus* in three studied populations from Bulgaria.

Fig. 4. Scatter plot of shell diameter versus shells depth in *Cyclopyxis puteus*.

ditional evidence for the cosmopolitan dispersion of *C. puteus* is that the species is registered also in Asia: Indonesia (Bonnet, 1992), Nepal (Bonnet, 1977b,

1981), North Korea (Golemansky & Todorov, 1991), Thailand (Bonnet, 1987; Golemansky & Todorov, 2000), Vietnam (Bobrov et al., 2010), Africa: Demo-

Table 2. Measurements of *Cyclopyxis puteus* according to current study and previous biometric records. The number of examined individuals is shown in brackets. Summarised data* – from Borisova Gradina and Mechata Dupka.

Source autors	Country	Location	Diameter	Depth	External opening	Internal opening	Invagination
Thomas 1960	France	Pessac	145–163	110–120	45–50	25–35	28–30
Golemansky 1962	Guinea	Rég de N'zérékoré area	164	120	—	36	48
Bobrov & Mazei 2004	Russia	Sikhote-Alin Reserve	120–132 (38)	130–180 (46)	—	34–46 (46)	—
Vincke et al 2006		Île de la Possession	195 (1)	—	—	—	—
Todorov & Bankov 2019	Bulgaria	summarised data*	133–179 (64)	94–120 (11)	32–54 (53)	27–38 (15)	—
current study	Bulgaria	Plachkovtsi Village	145–190 (350)	93–145 (350)	42–65 (350)	28–44 (329)	39–57 (84)
unpublished	Bulgaria	Borisova Gradina	133–180 (117)	96–121 (10)	32–61 (114)	27–42 (75)	28–36 (9)
unpublished	Bulgaria	Mechata Dupka	134–179 (58)	94–120 (11)	42–56 (47)	26–39 (47)	—

Fig. 5. Original drawings of Thomas 1960, modified: 1) ventral side; 2, 3) lateral side; 4) dorsal side.

cratic Republic of the Congo (Siemensma, 2019–2023); Gabon (Bonnet, 1969); Guinea (Golemansky, 1962); remote sub-Antarctic archipelago Îles Crozet (part of the French Southern and Antarctic Lands, Vincke et al., 2006) and even as part of Antarctic microbiota (Sudzuki, 1979). During the expedition in Guinea, Golemansky (1962) found shells that have the general appearance of *C. puteus*, but with much smaller dimensions (diameter 72 μm; depth 60 μm; pseudostome 18–20 μm; diameter/depth ration – 1.2; diameter/external opening – 4.0). No following de-

scription was made. Subsequently described as a variety – *Cyclopyxis puteus* var. *golemanskyi* Chardez, 1964 (Siemensma, 2019–2023), this morphotype is registered also in Belgium, North France, Luxemburg and Netherland (Chardez & Lambert, 1981) and terrestrial habitats of Antarctica (Sudzuki, 1979).

It must be noted that most of the records are based on single individuals or populations with very low density. This global distribution pattern must be interpreted with caution, given recent molecular studies that reveals species complexes with hidden

Fig. 6. Light (A, C, E) and scanning electron (B, D, F) photographs of *Cyclopyxis puteus*: (A, B) ventral side; (C, D) dorsal side; (E, F) profile.

(pseudo)cryptic diversity (Kosakyan et al., 2012, 2013, Singer et al., 2015) and different geographical distribution (Heger et al., 2013).

Additional data associated with geographical distribution is available at the Supplementary material 01 – Table A1 [🔗](#).

Fig. 7. SEM photographs of the ultrastructure: (A) ventral structure showing double contour; (B) structure of the external opening; (C) ventral side with numerous pores; (D) dorsal side.

Ecology

The type locality of *C. puteus* is a sandy soil of pine forest. Indeed, subsequent studies confirmed this species as inhabitant of forest litter, soils and mosses (Puytorac et al., 1970; Bonnet, 1977a, b, 1979, 1987, 1992; Chardez & Lambert, 1981, Lousier, 1982; Golemansky & Todorov, 1991, 2000, unpublished data; Balik, 1992, 1994, 1997; Bobrov, 2001; Todorov, 2001, unpublished data; Bobrov & Mazei, 2004; Vincke et al., 2004; Bobrov et al., 2010; 2013; Payne et al., 2020). Records of solitary specimens came from calcimorphic soil on karst (Bonnet, 1992), humic soil without plant cover (Balik, 1992), humus collected from bamboo roots (Bonnet, 1987), flooded savannah (Bonnet, 1997), rhizosphere of epiphytic plants and area with cut off forest, which was subse-

quently burned (Coûteaux & Chardez, 1981). Additional information about its ecological preferences is provided by Bonnet (1974), who registered it in both acidic and carbonated soils in Québec province, Canada. Accidental findings of *C. puteus* in *Sphagnum* mosses (Chardez et al., 1987; Golemansky & Todorov, 1991; Bankov, 2022) and freshwater habitats like a small swamp in rice field (Golemansky & Todorov, 1991) or forest stream (Golemansky & Todorov, 2000) may be due meteorological conditions like wind and/or heavy rain that brought single specimens from adjacent areas. Unfortunately, no differentiation has been made between live and dead specimens in previous studies, therefore the ecological characteristics of the habitats with single specimens or low population densities may not give us additional information about the ecology of the species.

Fig. 8. Worldwide localities of *Cyclopyxis puteus*.

In the studied populations from Bulgaria, the number of living individuals varies between 30–40 %. Samples were taken from beech (Plachkovtsi and Mechata Dupka) and oak (Borisova Gradina) forests, confirming conclusion that *Cyclopyxis puteus* is a soil and litter-dwelling species with occasional findings in peat bogs and freshwater habitats.

The next steps involve additional studies from different geographic areas to establish the phenotypic plasticity and ecological preferences of the species. Genetic characterisation is needed to provide evidences of its cosmopolitan distribution and/or the potential presence of (pseudo)cryptic diversity within *Cyclopyxis puteus*.

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References

Balik V. 1992 Testacean amoebae fauna (Protozoa, Rhizopoda, Testacea) from the Asian part of the USSR (Region of the Baikal lake and Khabarovsk). Acta Societatis Zoologicae Bohemoslovacae 56: 93–107.

- Balik V. 1994 Krytenky (Rhizopoda, Protozoa) oblasti Velké kotliny (Jeseníky, Česká republika). Časopis Slezského zemského muzea 43: 237–252.
- Balik V. 1997 Fauna krytenek (Protozoa, Testacea) západní části Národního parku (Slovenská republika). Štúdie o Tatranskom Národného parku 2 (35): 103–122.
- Bankov N. 2022 Composition, distribution and ecological characteristics of testate amoebae from Sphagnum mosses in Bulgaria. Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences. PhD thesis, 1–170.
- Beyens L., Chardez D., De Baere D., De Bock P., Jacques E. 1990 Ecology of Terrestrial Testate Amoebae Assemblages from Coastal Lowlands on Devon Island (NWT, Canadian Arctic). Polar Biology 10: 431–440.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00233691>
- Bobrov A. 2001 Finding of the tropical group testate amoebae (Protozoa: Testacea) at the Far East (Sikhote Alin Reserve). Biology Bulletin of the Russian Academy of Sciences 28 (4): 401–407.
<https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1016631325774>
- Bobrov A., Mazei Y. 2004 Morphological Variability of Testate Amoebae (Rhizopoda: Testacealobosea: Testaceafilosea) in Natural Populations. Acta Protozoologica 43: 133–146.
- Bobrov A., Siegert C., Andreev A., Schirrmeister L. 2003 Testaceans (Protozoa: Testacea) in Quaternary permafrost sediments of Bykovsky Peninsula, Arctic Yakutia. Biology Bulletin of the Russian Academy of Sciences 30: 191–206.
<https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1023201624996>
- Bobrov A., Andreev A., Schirrmeister L., Siegert C. 2004 Testate amoebae (Protozoa: Testacealobosea and Testaceafilosea) as bioindicators in the Late Quaternary deposits of the Bykovsky Peninsula, Laptev Sea, Russia. Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology 209: 165–181.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.palaeo.2004.02.012>
- Bobrov A., Mazei Y., Tiunov A. 2010 Testate Amoebae of a Monsoon Tropical Forest of South Vietnam. Acta Protozoologica 49: 311–325.
- Bobrov A., Krasilnikov P., García-Calderón N.E. 2013 Biogeography of testate amoebae in the soils of Mexico. Biodiversity and Conservation 22 (12): 2837–2855.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-013-0558-5>
- Bobrov A., Mazei Y., Buyvolova A., Yacher L. 2019 Testate Amoebae of Peru: filling the gap in the Neotropics. Revista de Biología Tropical 67 (3): 478–489.
<https://doi.org/10.15517/rbt.v67i3.32909>
- Bonnet L. 1969 Aspects généraux du peuplement thécamoebien édaphique de l’Afrique intertropicale. In: Subsídios para o estudo de biologia na Lunda. Publicações Culturais da Companhia de Diamantes de Angola 81: 137–176.
- Bonnet L. 1972 Aspects généraux du peuplement thecamoebien des sols de l’Auvergne. Annales de la Station biologique de Besse-en-Chandesse (6–7): 1–20.
- Bonnet L. 1974 Quelques aspects du peuplement thécamoebien des sols de la Province de Québec (Canada). Canadian Journal of Zoology 52: 29–41.
<https://doi.org/10.1139/z74-006>
- Bonnet L. 1977a Faunistique et biogéographie des thécamoebiens I: Thécamoebiens des sols du Mexique. Bulletin de la Société d’Histoire Naturelle de Toulouse 113: 40–44.
- Bonnet L. 1977b Le peuplement Thécamoebien des sols du Népal et son intérêt biogéographique. Bulletin de la Société d’Histoire Naturelle de Toulouse 113: 331–348.
- Bonnet L. 1979 Faunistique et biogéographie des thécamoebiens V: Thécamoebiens des quelques sols du Brésil et du Paraguay. Bulletin de la Société d’Histoire Naturelle de Toulouse 115: 119–122.
- Bonnet L. 1981 L’intérêt biogéographique du peuplement thécamoebien des sols du Népal. Paléogéographie et Biogéographie de l’Himalaya et du sous-continent indien, éditions du C.N.R.S., Paris: 53–60.
- Bonnet L. 1987 Faunistique et biogéographie des Thécamoebiens. IX- Thécamoebiens de quelques sols forestiers de Thaïlande (2ème partie). Bulletin de la Société d’Histoire Naturelle de Toulouse 123: 115–121.
- Bonnet L. 1992 Faunistique et Biogéographie des Thécamoebiens. X- Thécamoebiens de quelques sols d’Indonésie (Deuxième partie). Bulletin de la Société d’Histoire Naturelle de Toulouse 128: 17–21.
- Bonnet L. 1993 Communautés thécamoebiennes édaphiques partiellement rélictuelles dans le Sud

- Ouest de la France. Bulletin de la Société d'Histoire Naturelle de Toulouse 129: 7–14.
- Chardez D. 1961 Catalogue des Thécamoebiens de Belgique. Bulletin de l'Institut Faculté Agronomique des Stations de Recherches de Gembloux 29: 269–300.
- Chardez D., Lambert J. 1981 Thécamoebiens indicateurs biologiques (Protozoa Rhizopoda testacea). Bulletin des Recherches Agronomiques de Gembloux 16 (3): 181–204.
- Chardez D., Beyens L., Bock P. 1987 Thécamoebiens de Campine (Protozoa Rhizopoda Testacea). Bulletin des Recherches Agronomiques de Gembloux 22 (4): 285–300.
- Coûteaux M.-M., Chardez D. 1981 Thécamoebiens édaphiques et muscicoles de Guyane Française. Revue d'écologie et de biologie du sol 18 (2): 193–208.
- Decloître L. 1977 Le Genre *Cyclopyxis*. Compléments à jour au 31. décembre 1974 de la Monographie du genre parue en 1929. Archiv für Protistenkunde 119: 31–53.
- Deltshev C., Beron P., Blagoev G., Golemansky V., Peneva V., Stoev P., Todorov M., Hubenov Z. 1999 Faunistic Diversity of Invertebrates (non Insecta) of Central Balkan National Park. In: Sakalian M. (ed.) Biological Diversity of the Central Balkan National Park. USAID, 289–317.
- Golemansky V. 1962 Faune muscicole de Guinée forestière (Rhizopodes testacés). Recherches Africaines. Études guinéennes (Nouvelle Série) 4: 33–62.
- Golemansky V. 1970 A list of Testacea (Protozoa, Rhizopoda) from the Duszatyńskie Lakes in Poland. Fragmenta faunistica 16: 21–25.
- Golemansky V., Todorov M. 1991 Faune thécamoebienne (Rhizopoda, Testacea) de la Corée du Nord. Acta zoologica bulgarica 41: 3–10.
- Golemansky V., Todorov M. 2000 Testate amoebae (Protozoa, Rhizopoda) from Thailand. Acta Protozoologica 39 (3): 337–344.
- Heger T.J., Mitchell E.A.D., Leander B.S. 2013 Holarctic phylogeography of the testate amoeba *Hyalosphenia papilio* (Amoebozoa: Arcellinida) reveals extensive genetic diversity explained more by environment than dispersal limitation. Molecular Ecology 22: 5172–5184. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mec.12449>
- Kang S., Tice A.K., Spiegel F.W., Silberma, J.D., Pánek T., Cepicka I., Kostka M., Kosakyan A., Alcântara D.M.C., Roger A.J., Shadwick L.L., Smirnov A., Kudryavtsev A., Lahr D.J.G., Brown M.W. 2017 Between a pod and a hard test: The deep evolution of amoebae. Molecular Biology and Evolution 34 (9): 2258–2270. <https://doi.org/10.1093/molbev/msx162>
- Kosakyan A., Heger T.J., Leander B.S., Todorov M., Mitchell E.A.D., Lara E. 2012 COI barcoding of nebelid testate amoebae (Amoebozoa: Arcellinida): extensive cryptic diversity and redefinition of the Hyalospheniidae Schultze. Protist 163: 415–434. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.protis.2011.10.003>
- Kosakyan A., Goma F., Mitchell E.A.D., Heger T.J., Lara E. 2013 Using DNA-barcoding for sorting out protist species complexes: a case study of the *Nebela tinctoris-collaris-bohemica* group (Amoebozoa; Arcellinida, Hyalospheniidae). European Journal of Protistology 49: 222–237. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejop.2012.08.006>
- Kosakyan A., Goma F., Lara E., Lahr D.J. 2016 Current and future perspectives on the systematics, taxonomy and nomenclature of testate amoebae. European Journal of Protistology, 55: 105–117. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejop.2016.02.001>
- Lousier J.D. 1982 Colonization of Decomposing Deciduous Leaf Litter by Testacea (Protozoa, Rhizopoda): Species Succession, Abundance, and Biomass. Oecologia 52 (3): 381–388. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00367963>
- Nicholls K.H. 2005 *Cyclopyxis acmodonta* n. sp. and *Arcella formosa* n. sp.: two new species of testate rhizopods (Arcellinida, Protozoa) from remnant wetlands in Ontario, Canada. Canadian Field-Naturalist 119: 403–411. <https://doi.org/10.22621/cfn.v119i3.152>
- Payne R., Bobrov A., Tsyganov A., Babeshko K., Sloan T., Kay M., Kupriyankov D., Surkov N., Novenko E., Andreev A., Mazei Y. 2020 First records of contemporary testate amoeba assemblages from the Kamchatka Peninsula, Russia and potential for paleoenvironmental reconstruction. Boreas 50 (4): 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bor.12469>
- de Puytorac P., Mignot J.P., Grain J., Grolliere C.A., Bonnet L., Couillard P. 1972 Premier relevé de certains groupes de Protozoaires libres sur le territoire de la station de Biologie de l'Université de Montréal (Saint-Hippolyte, comté de

- Terrebonne, Québec). *Naturaliste Canadien* 99: 417–440.
- Siemensma F.J. 2019–2023 *Microworld*, world of amoeboid organisms. World-wide electronic publication, Kortenhoef.
<https://arcella.nl/>
- Singer D., Kosakyan A., Pillonel A., Mitchell E.A.D., Lara E. 2015 Eight species in the *Nebela collaris* complex: *Nebela gimlii* (Arcellinida, Hyalospheniidae), a new species described from a Swiss raised bog. *European Journal of Protistology* 51: 79–85.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejop.2014.11.004>
- Sudzuki M. 1979 On the Microfauna of the Antarctic Region III. Microbiota of the Terrestrial Interstices. Proceedings of the Symposium on terrestrial Ecosystems in the Syowa Station Area, *Memoirs of National Institute of Polar Research*, Special Issue 11: 104–126.
- Thomas R.M. 1960 Essai pour un Catalogue des Rhizopodes Testaces des biotopes terricoles. *Bulletin de la Société de pharmacie de Bordeaux* 99: 13–22.
- Todorov M. 2001 Testate Amoebae (Protozoa: Rhizopoda) in Soil and Litter of Beech Forests (*Fagus sylvatica* L.) from Bulgaria. *Acta zoologica bulgarica* 53 (2): 19–37.
- Todorov M., Bankov N. 2019 An Atlas of *Sphagnum*-Dwelling Testate Amoebae in Bulgaria. *Advanced Books*. Pensoft Publishers, Sofia, 286 pp.
<https://doi.org/10.3897/ab.e38685>
- Vincke S., van de Vijver B., Nijs I., Beyens L. 2006 Changes in the Testacean Community Structure Along Small Soil Profiles. *Acta Protozoologica* 45: 395–393.
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Supplementary materials

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